

“Job Description & Job Satisfaction of Library Professional’s working in C.P.E. Colleges Affiliated to SPPU Pune”

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Abstract:

This research paper deals with Job Description & Job Satisfaction of Library Professional’s Working in C.P.E. Colleges Affiliated to SPPU Pune. In this article included nine C.P.E. colleges. Researcher has adopted survey method and chosen questionnaire tool for data collection. Researcher has drafted standard questionnaire with the help of rating scale questions. Researcher has distributed 58 questionnaires and received 48 questionnaires from library professionals. Most of library professionals are satisfied in their job.

Keywords: Job Description, Job Satisfaction, Library Professional’s, C.P.E. college.

Introduction:

Job description and satisfaction are systematically evaluated in this research. Job satisfaction is a psychological concept and this concept is a modern approach to understand success and failures of library as an organization. The study focused on human behavioural, social status of library professionals, their interest and their satisfaction level of library professionals working in C.P.E. colleges affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune. Total nine colleges were got, ‘College with Potential for Excellence’ (C.P.E.) status from UGC to under SPPU, Pune. Researcher has selected survey method for this research work and choose questionnaire tool for data collection. In this questionnaire included some five rating scale questions for find out level of satisfaction of library professionals.

Review of Related Literature:

1. Reddy, K. Devendra (2014): Present book gives detail on “Job satisfaction among library professionals.” It is a research work. The study is related to know the job satisfaction level of library professionals in terms of pay and perks, promotions, nature of work, etc. As per the official records of AICTE, New Delhi, there are 92 engineering colleges in Rayalaseema region of Andhrapradesh as on June 2009.

2. Esakkimuthu, C. &Vellaichamy (2015): “Job Satisfaction among the library professionals in engineering institutes: An empirical study”. In their article measure the job satisfaction among library professionals in engineering institutions in Tamilnadu state.

3. Bellary, Ravi N. &Naik, Ramesh (2016): “Job Satisfaction of library and information science Professionals: An Expert’s View”. In this article focused on Job Satisfaction of LIS Professionals and found the expert’s view on different parameters of Job Satisfaction of LIS Professionals in national and international level.

4. Marasinghe, M.P.L.R. &Wijayaratne, Anusha (2018): “The Impact of gender Differences on Job Satisfaction of University Library Professionals”. This article represents the influence of gender on Job Satisfaction among University library professionals in Sri Lanka.

Objectives of the present study:

1. To know the job description of library professionals.
2. To know the level of job satisfaction of library professional staff.
3. To know the factors affecting job satisfaction.
4. To study the attitude of the library professional staff towards their job.
5. To identify the factors which improve satisfaction level of professional staff.

Research methodology:

Researcher has selected survey method for present research and chosen questionnaire tool for data collection.

Scope and Limitations:

Present research covered C.P.E. colleges affiliated to SPPU Pune. Nine colleges are included in this research. The study is based on job description and job satisfaction level of library professionals of these colleges. Data is collected from library professionals who got LIS education. This study is limited to only

C.P.E. colleges affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune.

Data Analysis and Data Interpretation:

Table No. 1
Do you undertake every kind of work in your library?

Sr. No.	Option	Response	Percentage
01	Yes	23	47.91%
02	No	11	22.91%
03	Some few section	09	18.75%
04	No Comments	05	10.41%
Total		48	100%

Above table no. shows that maximum 47.91% respondents are doing every kind of work in their library, 22.91% respondents are said

No, 18.75% respondents are doing work some few sections and 10.41% are not comments.

Table No. 2
Do you feel your job is challenging and interesting?

Sr. No.	Option	Response	Percentage
01	Yes	39	81.25%
02	No	01	2.08%
03	Can't say	04	8.33%
04	No Comments	04	8.33%
Total		48	100%

Table no. 2 reveals that 81.25% of respondents are felt their job is challenging and interesting, 8.33% are said can't say,

8.33% are said no comments and 2.08% said No respectively.

Table No. 3
Does your management take action against wrong performance?

Sr. No.	Option	Response	Percentage
01	Yes	26	54.16%
02	No	14	29.16%
03	Some time	05	10.41%
04	No comments	03	6.25%
Total		48	100%

Table no. 3 shows that 54.16% of respondents are felt management take action against wrong performance, 29.16% respondents are

said No, 10.41% respondents are said some time and 6.25% respondents are said no comments.

Table No. 4
Is library work fairly distributed among library staff?

Sr. No.	Option	Response	Percentage
01	Yes	45	93.75%
02	No	03	6.25%
Total		48	100%

Table no. 4 shows that 93.75% of respondents are said their library work fairly distributed among library staff and 6.25% of respondents are said No.

Table No. 5
Who solves general library problems occurs in routine functioning?

Sr. No.	Option	Response	Percentage
01	Self	13	27.08%
02	Library Committee	09	18.75%
03	Staff	14	29.16%
04	Management	12	25.00%
Total		48	100%

Table no. 5 indicated that 29.16% of respondents are said staff solves their general library problems occurs in routine functioning, 27.08% of respondents are said

self, 25.00% of respondents are said management and 18.75% of respondents are said library committee respectively.

Table No. 6
Are you satisfied with working environment in your college library?

Sr. No.	Option	Response	Percentage
01	Yes	45	93.75%
02	No	03	6.25%
	Total	48	100%

Table no. 6 reveals that 93.75% of respondents are satisfied with working environment in their college library and 6.25% of respondents are not satisfied.

Table No. 7
“Promotion goes to those who most deserve it”. Do you agree with this?

Sr. No.	Option	Response	Percentage
01	Agree	37	77.08%
02	Disagree	04	8.33%
03	No Comments	07	14.58%
	Total	48	100%

Table no. 7 shows that 77.08% of respondents are agree about promotion goes to those who most deserve it, 8.33% of respondents are

disagree and 14.58% of respondents are No Comments.

Table No. 8
Rate the level of accountability fixed at different hierarchical positions in the library.

Sr. No.	Level of Job Satisfaction	Response	Percentage
01	Disgruntled	02	4.16%
02	Dissatisfaction	04	8.33%
03	Moderate	09	18.75%
04	Satisfied	11	22.91%
05	Highly Satisfied	22	45.83%
	Total	48	100%

The data of above table reveal that 87.5% (level 5,4 & 3) respondents are satisfied with their accountable fix at different hierarchical

positions in the library. Only 12.5% (level 2 & 1) respondents have shown their level very low.

Table No. 9
Rate the level of library profession and its importance in the college and society.

Sr. No.	Level of Job Satisfaction	Response	Percentage
01	Disgruntled	00	00%
02	Dissatisfaction	01	2.08%
03	Moderate	07	14.58%
04	Satisfied	13	27.08%
05	Highly Satisfied	27	56.25%
	Total	48	100%

It is observed from above data that 97.91% (level 5, 4 & 3) of respondents reported that they are very satisfied with library profession

and its importance in the college and society and only 2.08% (level 2 & 1) of respondents are not satisfied.

Table No. 10, Rate the level of recognition you get after doing some creative work.

Sr. No.	Level of Job Satisfaction	Response	Percentage
01	Disgruntled	00	00%
02	Dissatisfaction	02	4.16%
03	Moderate	04	8.33%
04	Satisfied	17	35.41%

05	Highly Satisfied	25	52.08%
Total		48	100%

It is clear from above table no. 10 that 95.83% (level 5, 4 & 3) of respondents are satisfied with recognition after they doing

some creative work but 4.16% (level 2 & 1) of respondent's satisfaction level is very low.

Table No. 11
Rate the level of your satisfaction in enjoyment of your professional life.

Sr. No.	Level of Job Satisfaction	Response	Percentage
01	Disgruntled	01	2.08%
02	Dissatisfied	01	2.08%
03	Moderate	06	12.5%
04	Satisfied	21	43.75%
05	Highly Satisfied	19	39.58%
Total		48	100%

Above table shows that 95.83% (level 5, 4 & 3) of respondents are satisfied in enjoyment of their professional life and only 4.16% (level 2 & 1) of respondents are not satisfied in enjoyment of their professional life.

Conclusion & Findings:

Researcher selected C.P.E. colleges affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune for present research. Total 9 colleges got C.P.E. status under SPPU Pune. Researcher was distributed 58 questionnaires among colleges and received back 48 questionnaires. Total 82.75% respondents are given response from library professionals working in C.P.E. colleges. Some major findings are given below:

All CPE college library is well developed and fulfil the C.P.E. criteria given by UGC.

This research found 47.91% of library professionals are doing every kind of work in their library.

Most of 81.25% of professionals are felt their job is challenging and interesting.

Maximum 93.75% of professionals are said their library work fairly distributed among library staff.

It is found that 93.75% of professionals are satisfied with working environment in their college library.

This study reveals that 77.08% of professionals are agree about, "Promotion goes to those who most deserve it".

Majority 87.5% of library professionals are satisfied with their accountable fix at different hierarchical positions in the library.

Maximum 97.91% of professional's satisfaction level is very high about profession and its importance in the college and society.

It is found that 95.83% of library professionals are satisfied in enjoyment of their professional life.

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